

**DISTRIBUTION OF WEED SEED BANK FLOODED SOILS WITH
REFERENCE TO INVASIVE WOODY WEED
SPECIES *Amorpha fruticosa*, L.**

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*SUMMARY: Determination of soil weed seed bank is especially important for study of weed population dynamics as well as for planned weed control. During 2013 and 2014 soil sampling and determination of the number of weed species seed was performed on the flooded areas of the Danube. Analysis of the soil weed seed bank from locality Futog, showed that in the top soil layer of 0-10 cm, seeds of weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* L. had the highest abundance, comparing to other two soil layers, numbering 1276 seeds per m².*

Key words: seed bank, *Amorpha fruticosa* L., bush, invasive species.

INTRODUCTION

Weed seeds from plant reach the soil surface where they represent future soil weed seed bank (Konstantinović, 2008). Seed quantity and density in great extent depend on soil type, preceding crops, soil tillage, as well as on herbicide use (Konstantinović et al., 2008). Soil weed seed bank impacts on distribution of annual (Steinmann and Klingebiel, 2004), as well as perennial weed species (Blumenthal and Jordan, 2001), which has effect to the spread of weed community over the years. In perennial agrophytocenoses, such as vineyards it is less likely that dramatic changes would occur in composition of weed seed bank. Reduced soil tillage and use of mineral fertilizers, as well as permanent weed composition are restrictions that beside compact soil and inconvenient soil water regime can effect to the occurrence of weeds and weed seed bank composition (Le'ge`re et al., 2005, Smith and Gross, 2006). During 2012 in canals of the Public Water Management Company "Vode Vojvodine" phytocenological screenings confirmed presence of woody

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weed species on canal banks and slopes such as *Amorpha fruticosa* L., *Prunus spinosa* L., *Morus spp.*, *Crataegus laevigata* (Poir) DC, *Populus nigra* L., *Populus alba* L., *Populus tremula* L. and *Rubus caesius* L., while on certain localities occur also *Sambucus nigra* L. and *Salix alba* L. Weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* L. is a bush with a lot of grey branches. It flowers by the end of May and in June. *Amorpha fruticosa* L. (Fabaceae) is a bush of 1-3 (6) m in height, it can be tree like, branches are thin and erect. Purple flowers are in spiked inflorescences on the top of the branches. It grows well on embankments, roads and railways slots, it is used for reforestation of salt marsh, it is important for beekeeping. Flowering period lasts 20 to 25 days, immediately after Acacia, during the period without other significant bee pasture. It belongs to the honey weed species, which in the last five to ten years are also suitable for bees, which indicates great distribution of this woody weed species on the territory of Vojvodina. Acacia is suitable for reforestation of escarpments, slopes and landslides, because the root binds soil well. It is also used for windbreaks belts, hedges and as ornamental shrubs in parks. Root system of this weed species is surface, anastomosis like. During germination of "seeds" (monograin beans), from radicle first develops tiny root out of which grows axial root with lateral roots that anchor to the soil out of which they absorb water and minerals (Tucović and Isajev, 2001). On the flooded meadows *A. fruticosa* L. prevents development of existing vegetation (Botta-Dukat, 2005). This weed species is also described as invasive weed species of Central Europe (Weber and Gut, 2004; Dumitrascu et al., 2010).

Weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* L. is usually found in swamps, on the canals and ponds, as well as in flooded forests (Fargione, 2005) or purely vegetated banks, reeds and high halophyte habitats (Anastasiu et al., 2007). On canal banks and slopes grass weeds are necessary for prevention of erosion on certain canal sections, but broadleaved weeds are necessary to be controlled. According to the study of Pantelić et al. (2003) dominant weeds near canal network are *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Erigeron canadensis*, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, *Daucus carota*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Sorghum halepense*. On canal banks and slopes there are numerous woody weed species such as *Amorpha fruticosa*, *Rubus caesius* and *Prunus spinosa* (Pantelić et al., 2003).

At ruderal sites, weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* L. is efficiently controlled by the following herbicides: glyphosate (products Glifosat-Zorka, Glifol, Roundup, Cidoherb, Glifosat SL-480, Glifosav-480, Pirokor, Glitotal-480, Agroglifosat, Agroglifosat eco, Agrototal, Glifosat BN-480, Sirkosan, Glifosol-48, Cosmic-36, Boom-efekt, Clinic 480-SL, Glyfos, Glifomark, Bingo-480, Fozat-480, Dominator, Uragan/Sistem-4, Glyphogan 480-SL, Titan, Touč-down 4-LC) and triclopyr (the product Garlon 4) (Konstantinović, 2011). Knowledge on capability of fast vegetative propagation of emergent and woody species and their huge biomass, suggests that mechanical control is costly and inadequate control measure. Besides uneconomical manual mowing, mechanical mowing cuts plants to smaller parts, and plant regeneration causes repeated formation of huge phytomass. Hitherto studies on control of aquatic, especially emergent and woody weeds suggest that there exists need for several years lasting herbicide use, as the most efficient and the most economical way of their elimination (Konstantinović, 2011). Biological weed invasion represents great danger for keeping of biological diversity, causing extinction of autohton species and change of ecosystem functions. Among numerous factors, success of invasion depends upon biological properties of the invasive weed, as well as on availability of the habitat resources (Rejmanek et al., 2005). Wetlands are especially prone to invasion due to

highly changeable environmental humidity regime (Pino *et al.*, 2006) and light dispersal of propagules by water (Pysek *et al.*, 2004). Invasive wetland plants have significant impact to soil structure and biodiversity (Zedler & Kercher, 2004), but it should have in mind that wetlands are less prone to changes, at least in terms of dramatic ecosystem transformations (Pysek *et al.*, 2004).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The soil sampling was performed at localities Futog and Begeč, on the coastal area of Danube (flood zone before the dam). The both of the studied localities consist of alluvial soil type, and they are flood zones due to high Danube water level. At the chosen locality that was about 10 ha, soil sampling was done up to depth of 0-30cm with ten replications per diagonal. Soil sampling was performed by a probe that was 4.5 cm in diameter. Soil samples were taken from depths of 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm, and each sample from three soil depths contained about 3 kg of the soil (Smutný and Křen, 2002). The soil was sieved through a series of copper sieves of 0.25 mm in diameter. After that followed weed seed separation from soil samples, and their determination. Determination and number of weed species seeds was accomplished by microscope, as well as by weed classifiers (Janjić and Kojić, 2003). The classified weed seeds were disinfected in 0.1% solution of fungicide benomyl, and then placed into climatic chamber for germination in controlled conditions. Climatic chamber parameters were set to 12 h illumination period at 25 °C ($52.4 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and to 12 h at 18°C without illumination, air humidity was 65%. Petri dishes 100x90mm in size were covered by polyethylene leaves in order to avoid evaporation. Check on number of germinated determined seeds was performed each two days. After 28 days aboveground and underground parts of each germinated seed were measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the studied localities, in weed seed bank the total of 19 weed species were identified: *Amorpha fruticosa*, *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, *Brassica rapa*, *Chenopodium album*, *Chenopodium hybridum*, *Urtica dioica*, *Euphorbia helioscopia*, *Galium aparine*, *Mentha arvensis*, *Portulaca oleracea*, *Polygonum aviculare*, *Polygonum lapathifolium*, *Rumex crispus*, *Setaria glauca*, *Setaria viridis*, *Stellaria media*, *Solanum nigrum*, and *Trifolium repens*. The greatest number of weed species was identified in the first two soil layers of 0-10 and 10-20cm. *Amorpha fruticosa* seed were also determined only in the first two layers at the both of the studied localities. In the first layer of 0-10 cm at locality Futog, 1276 seeds of weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* were found per m², in the second layer 877 seeds were determined, and in the third studied layer there were 319 seeds per m². At locality Futog the seed of weed species *Stellaria media* in the soil layer of 10-20 cm had the highest distribution, numbering 2951 plants per m² (Figure 1). In climatic chamber germinated seeds of the following weed species: *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Amorpha fruticosa*, *Stellaria media*, *Urtica dioica* and *Setaria glauca*.

Figure 1. Number of weed species seeds per m² at locality Futog

Low variation percentage (V%) suggests that seeds of certain weed species were evenly distributed in all three studied soil layers. Extremely high variation percentage shows that seeds of one weed species occur unevenly in soil layers, i.e. that in some soil layer there is greater number of them than in other, or it cannot be found. In Table 1 the lowest variation coefficient of 31.22% was recorded for weed species *Stellaria media*, while the highest value of 141.42% was recorded for weed species *Brassica rapa*, *Polygonum aviculare*, *Polygonum lapathifolium*, *Setaria glauca* and *Rumex crispus*.

Table 1. Statistical data processing by standard deviation and variation coefficient at locality Futog

Weed species	Number of weed seeds in samples from different soil depths X			Σ 0-30	Standard deviation	V%
	0 - 10	10 - 20	20 - 30			
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	16	22	8	46	5.73	37.40
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	4	12	3	19	4.03	63.59
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	16	11	4	31	4.92	47.63
<i>Brassica rapa</i>	2	0	0	2	0.94	141.42
<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	3	2	0	5	1.25	74.83
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	0	7	0	7	3.30	141.42
<i>Polygonum lapathifolium</i>	0	0	3	3	1.41	141.42
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	0	14	6	20	5.73	86.02
<i>Rumex crispus</i>	0	3	0	3	1.41	141.42
<i>Setaria glauca</i>	0	2	0	2	0.94	141.42
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	0	2	6	8	2.49	93.54
<i>Stellaria media</i>	20	37	20	77	8.01	31.22
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	0	3	5	8	2.49	93.54
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	30	26	5	61	10.96	53.92
TOTAL	91	140	61	292		

Standard deviation indicates the average deviation of the number of seeds of each weed species from arithmetic mean of the number of seeds of the given weed in all three depths of the sampled soil. The highest value of standard deviation of determined weed seeds at locality Futog was recorded for weed species *Urtica dioica*, while the lowest value was found for weed species *Brassica rapa* and *Setaria glauca*. Table 1 also shows presence of the highest number of weed seeds in the soil layer of 10-20cm, which was to be expected because the studied soils were overflowed soils in which the top soil layer in great measure changes in terms of weed seed bank composition.

At locality Begeč, 17 seeds of weed species were determined, and according to the number of seeds weed species *Stellaria media* with 2472 seeds per m² proved to be the most numerous in the soil layer 10-20cm (Figure 2). At locality Begeč, in the top soil layer of 0-10 cm, 1037 seeds of weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* were found per m², in the second layer were found 558 seeds and in the third 160 seeds per m². Figure 2 shows greater presence of highest number of seeds of weed species in the soil layer of 10-20cm, and the lowest in the soil layer of 20-30 cm.

Figure 2. Number of seeds of weed species per m² at locality Begeč

In Table 2, the lowest value of variation coefficient was from 25.26% and 27 % , recorded for weed species *Amaranthus retroflexus* and *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, while the highest value of 141.42% was recorded for weed species *Chenopodium hybridum*, *Polygonum lapathifolium*, *Galium aparine*, *Setaria viridis* *Solanum nigrum*, *Sorghum halepense* and *Rumex crispus*. The lowest value of variation coefficient had seeds of three weed species, distributed only in one of three studied soil layers. For weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* at locality Begeč did not exist uniform value of determined seeds of this species at all three studied soil depths. Value of variation coefficient for weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* at locality Begeč of 61.32% (Table 2) was higher than at locality Futog where it was 47.63%, i.e. at locality Begeč there exists higher concentration of weed seeds in some of the layers, and at locality Futog that difference was significantly lower. Table 2 also shows that the medium soil layer of 10-20cm had the greatest number of weed seeds (138) which was for more than 50% higher in comparison to the deepest soil layer.

Table 2. Statistical data processing by standard deviation and variation coefficient at locality Begeč

Weed Species	Number of weed seeds in samples from different soil depths (X)			Σ 0-30	Standard deviation	V%
	0 - 10	10 - 20	20 - 30			
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	23	19	12	54	4.55	25.26
<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	9	10	5	24	2.16	27.00
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	13	7	2	22	4.50	61.32
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	6	13	7	26	3.09	35.67
<i>Chenopodium hybridum</i>	0	2	0	2	0.94	141.42
<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i>	2	5	0	7	2.05	88.06
<i>Galium aparine</i>	0	7	0	7	3.30	141.42
<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	4	7	0	11	2.87	78.20
<i>Polygonum lapathifolium</i>	0	0	5	5	2.36	141.42
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	12	16	4	32	4.99	46.77
<i>Rumex crispus</i>	0	0	4	4	1.89	141.42
<i>Setaria viridis</i>	0	5	0	5	2.36	141.42
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	0	2	0	2	0.94	141.42
<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	0	3	0	3	1.41	141.42
<i>Stellaria media</i>	16	31	20	67	6.34	28.40
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	3	1	2	6	0.82	40.82
<i>Veronica polita</i>	2	3	0	5	1.25	74.83
TOTAL	103	138	63	304		

CONCLUSION

The highest number of germinated weed seeds, determined at locality Futog had weed species *Amaranthus retroflexus* and *Stellaria media*. At locality Begeč the highest number of germinated seeds had three determined weed species *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Chenopodium album* and *Stellaria media*. At both of localities those were weed species that were dominant in weed seed bank. At locality Futog, number of seeds of weed species *Amorpha fruticosa* was 2472 per m² in all three soil layers. In the second soil layer of 10-20 cm seeds of this weed species prevail, numbering 140 seeds, taking into consideration that it is flooded soil in which seeds of weed species are hardly present in the top layer. At locality Begeč, where the soil is also flooded, number of seeds of this weed species was 1755 per m². At locality Begeč seeds of *Amorpha fruticosa* were present mostly in the top soil layer numbering 1037 seeds per m². At both localities, soil is often flooded. Flooded soils can have more or less concentration of seeds in the top layer, due to great impact of water regime.

REFERENCES

- ANASTASIU, P., GAVRIL, N., CORINA, B., CULIT, S. & ADRIAN, O.: A preliminary study on the neophytes of wetlands in Romania, Rabitsch, W., F. Essl & F. Klingenstein (Eds.): Biological Invasions - from Ecology to Conservation. Neobiota, 7:181-192, 2007.
- BOTTA-DUKAT, Z.: Invasion of alien species to Hungarian (semi-) natural habitats. Acta Botanica Hungarica. 50 (Suppl). p. 219–227, 2005.
- DUMITRASCU, M., GRIGORESCU I., NASTASE, M., DRAGOTA, C. AND KUCSICSA, G.: The Main Environmental Driving Forces of the Invasive Plant Species in the Romanian Protected Areas. Balowois 2010 – Ohrid. Republic of Macedonia – 25. 29 May 2010.
- FARGIONE, J.E., TILMAN, D.: Diversity decreases invasion via both sampling and complementary effects. Ecology Letters, 8: 604-611, 2005.
- BLUMENTHAL, D. M., AND JORDAN, N. R.: Weeds in field margins: a spatially explicit simulation analysis of *Cirsium arvense* population dynamics. Weed Science, 49: 509-519, 2001.
- JANJIĆ, V., KOJIĆ, M.: Atlas travnih korova. Institut za istraživanja u poljoprivredi „Srbija”, Beograd., 2003.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B.: Korovi i njihovo suzbijanje. Udžbenik. Poljoprivredni fakultet, Novi Sad, 2008.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B., MESELDŽIJA, M. AND KONSTANTINOVIĆ, BO.: Distribution of weed species seed under different crops and in various soil layers. Polish Journal of Natural Science, (Supplement), 5:298-299, 2008.
- KONSTANTINOVIĆ, B.: Osnovi herbologije i herbicidi. Udžbenik. Poljoprivredni fakultet Novi Sad, 2011.
- LE'GE'RE, A., STEVENSON, F. C., BENOIT, L. D. AND SAMSON, N.: Seedbank-plant relationships for 19 weed taxa in spring barley-red clover cropping systems. Weed Sci., 53:640–650, 2005.
- PINO, J., SEGUI, J.M. & ALVAREZ, N.: Invasibility of four plant communities in the Llobregat delta (Catalonia, NE of Spain) in relation to their historical stability. Hydrobiologia, 570: 257-263, 2006.
- PYSEK, P., RICHARDSON, D.M., REJMANEK, M., WEBSTER, G.L., WILLIAMSON, M. & KIRSCHNER, J.: Alien plants in checklists and floras: towards better communication between taxonomists and ecologists. Taxon, 51(1)131-143, 2004.
- REJMANEK, M., RICHARDSON, D.M. & PYSEK, P.: Plant invasions and invasibility of plant communities. In: Van der Maarel E. (Ed.): Vegetation Ecology. Blackwell Science, Oxford, pp. 32-355, 2005.
- PANTELIĆ, P., BUNČIĆ, N., ŠOVLJANSKI, R.: Hidrosistemi Dunav-Tisa-Dunav, Istorijat, značaj i suzbijanje korova u kanalskoj mreži. In: Akvatični korovi suzbijanje i posledice (R. Šovljanski, B. Konstantinović, i Z. Klokočar-šmit). Poljoprivredni fakultet Novi Sad i JVP „Vode Vojvodine“, 2003.
- SMITH, R. G. AND GROSS, K. L.: Rapid changes in the germinable fraction of the weed seed bank in crop rotations. Weed Sci., 54:1094–1100, 2006.
- SMUTNY, V., KREN, J.: Improvement of an elutriation method for estimation of weed seed bank in the soil, rostlinna výroba 48: 271-278, 2002.
- STEINMANN, H. H. AND KLINGEBIEL, L.: Secondary dispersal, spatial dynamics

and effects of herbicides on reproductive capacity of a recently introduced population of *Bromus sterilis* in an arable field. *Weed Res.*, 44:388–396, 2004.

TUCOVIĆ, A., ISAJEV, V.: Karakteristike i varijabilnost klijavaca bagrenca (*Amorpha fruticosa* L.) - korovske vrste plavnih stanista. *Acta herbologica*, 9(1)101-111, 2001.

ZEDLER, J.B. & KERCHER, S.: Causes and Consequences of Invasive Plants in Wetlands: Opportunities, Opportunists, and Outcomes. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 23(5)431-452, 2004.

WEBER, E., GUT, D.: Assessing the risk of potentially invasive plant species in central Europe. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 12:171-179, 2004.

**ZASTUPLJENOST BANKE SEMENA KOROVA PLAVNIH ZEMLJIŠTA S
OSVRTOM NA INVAZIVNU DRVENASTU KOROVSKU VRSTU
Amorpha fruticosa, L.**

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Izvod

Determinacija zemljišne banke semena korovskih biljaka je od izuzetnog značaja kako za izučavanje dinamike populacije korova tako i za plansko suzbijanje korova. Tokom 2013. i 2014. godine urađeno je uzorkovanje zemljišta, kao i određivanje brojnosti semena korovskih vrsta na plavnom području Dunava. Analizom banke semena korovskih vrsta istraživanih u blizini lokaliteta Futog, konstatovano je da u površinskom sloju zemljišta 0-10cm postoji najveća brojnost semena korovskih vrsta *Amorpha fruticosa* L., koja iznosi 1276 po m², u odnosu na druga dva dublja sloja zemljišta.

Key words: banka semena, *Amorpha fruticosa* L., žbun, invazivna vrsta.

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